

Sampling Method for Leaching Testing of Lead Perovskite-Silicon Tandem Photovoltaic Modules

Matthias Hämmer, Birgit Reinelt, Karsten Wambach

bifa Umweltinstitut GmbH, Augsburg, 86167, Germany

Abstract — As a result of field failure or improper treatment of end-of-life modules, toxic chemicals may leach out of photovoltaic (PV) modules. Moreover, the leaching out behavior decides about the legal classification into non-hazardous or hazardous waste in various jurisdictions. Consequently, this is an important property to study for PV modules. However, the preparation of representative samples from PV modules is not straightforward due to their inhomogeneity and size. Since 2022, there is a standard practice for sampling in the US while no standardization was made in the EU, so far. In this contribution, a complementary mechanical sampling method is presented showing similar accuracy as the US standard practice, however, using simpler techniques. This new sampling method is tested and validated for lead-based perovskite-silicon tandem PV modules and crystalline silicon PV modules.

I. INTRODUCTION

Photovoltaics (PV) is one of the main clean and renewable energy options for the replacement of fossil energy sources and thereby a very important part of the transition towards a clean energy system. Demand is growing rapidly (above 50 TW by 2050) [1] pushed by the urgent actions to counteract climate changes [2]. In the same time, worldwide PV module wastes were estimated to be 100 kt in 2020 and could reach over 60 million tons by 2050 [3]. The large number of modules both in use and in the end-of-life (EoL) phase bear the potential environmental risk of hazardous metals leaching in the cases of in-field degradation or failure, e.g. due to extreme weather conditions, or improper disposal of EoL modules [4]. Moreover, there are leachate-concentration based waste standards in the US, Germany and Japan among others. The question of classification as hazardous or non-hazardous waste is also critical for recycling since the legal requirements for handling, transport and treatment of the EoL modules may depend on it. Consequently, the leaching behavior of PV modules is an important property to study. However, preparing representative samples for leaching tests from an inhomogeneous item such as a PV module is not straightforward. Thus, the published results vary strongly [4 and references therein]. Since 2022, the “Standard Practice for Sampling of Solar Photovoltaic Modules for Toxicity Testing” ASTM E3325-21 requires waterjet cutting sampling with sample pieces smaller than $9,5 \times 9,5 \text{ mm}^2$ in the US [5]. In a short survey comprising five German water-jet cutting companies, no supplier able to prepare samples according to the ASTM E3325-21 standard procedure could be identified.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the sampling approach: There are four different area type on the laminate area of the PV module: cell area, cell ribbon area, string ribbon area and, non-cell/non-ribbon area. Pieces from one lead-based perovskite-silicon PV module (PST 1) of each area type are shown as photographs. Details on sampling are found in the text.

Consequently, an alternative, complementary mechanical sampling method was developed with focus on practicability and reliability.

In this contribution, this method is presented. It is tested and validated using conventional crystalline Silicon (c-Si) and lead-based perovskite-Si tandem (PST) PV modules with special interest on the leaching behavior of lead. For lead-based perovskite solar cells lead toxicity and the potential leaching of lead into the environment is one obstacle in the large-scale deployment of this technology [6]. The difference between these module type and more conventional c-Si modules is not the total lead content, but the present form of it. In conventional c-Si cell modules 8-10 g/m^2 of lead are found

as metallization pastes and solder material [7]. The investigated lead perovskite-Si tandem PV module has an overall lead content of around 2 g/m². From the perovskite layer, lead is found to accumulate in the form of PbI₂ upon degradation [8]. Thus, the sample method enables the investigation of the differences in leaching behavior for different forms of lead in PV modules.

II. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

A. PV Modules

All five tested modules were full-sized and fully operational PV modules with Al frames and junction boxes. Details per module are given below:

PST 1: Perovskite-Silicon Tandem (2T), glass-glass module, year of manufacture: 2021

PST 2: Perovskite-Silicon Tandem (2T), glass-glass module, year of manufacture 2023

c-Si 1: monocrystalline Silicon, glass-PVF module, year of manufacture 2013

c-Si 2: monocrystalline Silicon, glass- PVF module, year of manufacture 2013

c-Si 3: polycrystalline Silicon, glass-PVF module, year of manufacture 2013

B. Mechanical Cutting Method

The investigated PV modules were cut using a disc grinder with diamond cutting disc into 20 x 20 mm² pieces. At least 100 pieces from all area types specified below were prepared this way per PV module.

C. Proportional Sampling Approach

Samples were prepared using the proportional sampling approach [9]. There are four different types of pieces: cell area, cell ribbon area, string ribbon area and, non-cell/non-ribbon area pieces (Fig. 1). One sample of 100 g consisted of 20 to 25 pieces. The respective masses were chosen representatively to the area ratio of the area types of the whole PV module. This sampling method and the limitation to the laminate area of the PV module are in accordance to ASTM E3325-21.

D. Leaching according to EN 12457-4

Leaching experiments were performed according to EN 12457-4 and DIN 38414-4. 100 g of the sample prepared as described above were filled into a borosilicate glass flask

together with 1000 ml deionized H₂O. The flask was overhead-shaken for 24 h. Afterwards, the solid was filtrated and the filtrate was acidified with HNO₃ (65%, pA, Chemsolute) and investigated via ICP-OES (Optima 8000, PerkinElmer). The following elements were analyzed: Cs, In, Si, Ag, Al, As, Ba, Cd, Cr, Cu, Hg, Mg, Mo, Na, Ni, Pb, S, Sb, Se, Sn and Zn.

D. Aging Experiments

Samples prepared as described above were aged in colorless borosilicate glass bottles at room temperature and ambient atmosphere for two months.

Fig. 2. Exemplary pieces from the cutting of the c-Si 1 module with all four different area types (cell area, cell ribbon area, string ribbon area and, non-cell/non-ribbon area) and one piece upside-down showing the back sheet. Details on sampling are found in the text.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Mechanical Cutting Method

The real pieces' dimensions varied from 15 to 25 mm with the average weight ranging from 4,4 to 4,6 g for the pieces from the perovskite Si tandem modules and 4,5 to 4,7 g for the pieces from the c-Si modules. With the varying real piece dimensions extremes as low as 3 g and as high as 6 g are also found. However, the overall variance in the pieces' weight range around 10%.

The larger piece size of 20 x 20 mm² differs from the ASTM E3325-21. It was chosen since DIN 38414-4 requires the investigation of the respective waste in the form as it is potentially landfilled. Size reduction is only necessary as far as it is required for the leaching experiments. The larger piece size reduces the sampling effort while the subsequent leaching experiments are still practical. This is in line with earlier results indicating that the size reduction to fragments smaller than 1 mm is leading to overestimation when assessing the

leaching potentials of PV modules [4, 9, 10]. Sinha et al. report that less than half of CdTe PV modules fragments generated when simulation worst-case intentional crushing while handling in landfill are smaller than 1 cm [10]. TamizhMani et al. showed that broken c-Si PV modules usually exhibit centimeter sized fragments [11]. Further, the glass itself is broken into smaller fragments still connected to the total, 20 x 20 mm² sized sample piece due to it being tempered. The leachant can interact with the sample via these cracks, too.

For the modules PST 1 and PST 2, the rear side glass is detached from the front side glass and the solar cell during sample preparation via mechanical cutting. This introduces an additional area for the leachant to interact with the sample.

However, glass coverage was for all modules and all sample pieces close to 100% despite the discussed cracks and the detachment for the PST modules and, thus, similar to the sample pieces prepared via ASTM E3325-21 [9].

B. Proportional Sampling Approach

The composition regarding the four types of area of the different samples prepared by the proportional sampling approach vary by only 1 wt.-%. Consequently, the reproducible preparation of respective samples is possible with this method – despite the larger piece size and therefore smaller total amount of pieces per sample compared to ASTM E3325-21. This is confirmed by the leaching experiments described in the following.

It has proven to be useful to prepare the 100 g sample from the cut pieces by weight for each type of area including respective corrections being part of the proportional sampling approach [9]. For instance, cell ribbon pieces consist of only 5% cell ribbon area and 95% cell area. The sampling effort is reduced compared to ASTM E3325-21 since with the larger piece size only around 20 to 25 pieces comprise one 100 g sample instead of around 100 pieces. Again, the reproducibility of this sampling approach is confirmed by the leaching experiments in the following.

C. Leaching according to EN 12457-4

Exemplary leaching results for four samples each prepared from one lead-based perovskite-silicon tandem PV module and one crystalline Silicon PV module are shown in Fig. 3 and 4. In the following, the discussion is limited to the leached Pb content due to its ecological relevance and the liquid recovered from the leaching test is referred to as eluate in line with EN 12457-4.

The Pb content in the eluate is shown in Fig. 4 and Table I.

Fig. 3. Elemental concentrations from ICP-OES measurements of S, Pb, Na, Mg, Si and Cs in four different samples prepared from the same lead-based perovskite-silicon tandem PV module (PST 2) in mg/l in the eluate.

Fig. 3. Elemental concentrations from ICP-OES measurements of S, Pb, Na, Mg, Si and Cs in four different samples prepared from the same crystalline Silicon PV module (c-Si 3) in mg/l in the eluate.

Fig. 4. Pb content in leachate for five modules: The average value and the standard deviation are shown. The red dotted line on top of the graph represents the regulatory limit for the Pb content in the eluate.

TABLE I
LEAD CONTENT IN ELUATE FOR FRESH SAMPLES

Sample	Average Pb in eluate in mg/l	Standard Deviation	Variance
PST 1	0,27	0,04	15%
PST 2	0,31	0,06	19%
c-Si 1	0,16	0,04	28%
c-Si 2	0,11	0,01	9%
c-Si 3	0,17	0,02	13%

The average Pb contents in the eluate are 0,27 mg/l and 0,31 mg/l for the PST modules. These values are higher than for the c-Si modules with Pb contents in the eluate ranging from 0,11 to 0,16 mg/l for the c-Si modules. After aging, an increased Pb content in the eluate could be observed for the PST modules. This aging behavior is investigated in the subsequent chapter in detail. In Germany, the regulatory limit of Pb in eluates for the classification as hazardous waste is 1 mg/l based on landfill regulations [12]. This limit is not exceeded by any of the tested modules.

In comparison, samples from PV modules tested by TCLP (EPA method 1311) and WET procedures can be expected to have higher amounts of leachates due to the more aggressive, i.e. acidic solvent compare to elution according to EN 12457-4 [4]. Consequently, the relevant legal limits for Pb in the leachate are 1 mg/l in Germany and 5 mg/l in the US:

The variances listed in Table I range from 15 to 19% for PST modules and 9 to 28% for c-Si modules. This indicated similar accuracy as the ASTM E3325-21 standard practice using waterjet cutting (variance of 8%) [4, 9].

Fig. 3. Exemplary sample pieces (PST 1) aged for two months in ambient condition showing a yellowish coating formed during aging.

D. Aging Behavior and Influence on Leaching Results

Moreover, the aging behavior was investigated. This is relevant if the sampling is performed e.g. on site of the producer but the leaching experiments are outsourced to commercial laboratories. A two-month aging of the prepared samples in ambient conditions (Fig. 5) resulted in a strongly increased Pb content in the eluate of 0,62 mg/l. This could be the result of the formation of solid PbI_2 on top of the samples [8]. However, the aging behavior needs further investigation.

E. Discussion

For the new mechanical sampling method, results indicate a similar variance of results compared to the ASTM E3325-21 standard practice. However, the effort and complexity of sampling is reduced compared to waterjet cutting when using a disk grinder. The simple sampling method could enable PV producers to perform the sampling on-site eliminating the need to transport the PV module to a suited waterjet cutting facility. Further, the required time for sampling itself can be expected to be reduced with the new approach, too. Thus, the interval between sampling and leaching can be kept as short as possible which is relevant in the case of perovskite photovoltaics due to the aging behavior discussed above.

Another aspect relevant for the water-jet sampling of perovskite or PST PV modules is the possible reaction of the perovskite layer with water at the cutting surface leading to distorted leaching results. This potential issue could be circumvented by the proposed mechanical sampling method excluding any contact of the sample with water during the procedure.

In general, the mechanical sampling method presented herein can be applied to other products or wastes with layered, homogeneous structures.

IV. CONCLUSION

A new mechanical sampling method for leaching testing of photovoltaic modules is presented in this contribution. 20 x 20 mm² pieces were cut using a disc grinder. From these pieces, samples with 100 g weight each were prepared following the proportional sampling approach. Leaching experiments were performed according to EN 12457-4 in deionized water. The results of the Pb contents in the eluates of 0,27 to 0,31 mg/l for lead-based perovskite-Si tandem PV modules and 0,11 to 0,16 mg/l for the crystalline Silicon PV modules showed similar variance compared to the ASTM E3325-21 standard practice using waterjet cutting. Compared to the standard practice, the presented mechanical sampling approach offers a less complex and less time-consuming alternative.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors thank Tobias Graff for the disk cutting of the modules.

This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 958223; project PHOTORAMA.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ram M. et. al., Global energy system based on 100% renewable energy, study by Lappeenranta University of Technology and Energy Watch Group, Lappeenranta, Berlin, March 2019.
- [2] COP 21 Paris Agreement:
<https://unfccc.int/resource/docs/2015/cop21/eng/10a01.pdf>
- [3] G. A. Heath, T. J. Silverman, M. Kempe, M. Deceglie, D. Ravikumar, T. Remo, H. Cui, P. Sinha, C. Libby, S. Shaw, K. Komoto, K. Wambach, E. Butler, T. Barnes, A. Wade, *Nat Energy* **2020**, 5, 502.
- [4] F. Li, S. Shaw, C. Libby, N. Preciado, B. Bicer, G. TamizhMani, *Waste Management* **2024**, 174, 646.
- [5] E44 Committee, Standard Practice for Sampling of Solar Photovoltaic Modules for Toxicity Testing. ASTM E3325-21, **2022**, ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA.
- [6] P. Su, Y. Liu, J. Zhang, C. Chen, B. Yang, C. Zhang, X. Zhao, *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.* **2020**, 11, 2812.
- [7] P. Gebhardt, S. Hoffmann, T. Wenzel, L. Friedrich, S. Herceg, D. M. Subasi, De Rose, Angela, Lorenz, A., D. Philipp in *WCPEC-8, 8th World Conference on Photovoltaic Energy Conversion*, Milan, **2022**.
- [8] V. K. Ravi, B. Mondal, V. V. Nawale, A. Nag, *ACS omega* **2020**, 5, 29631.
- [9] G. TamizhMani, S. Shaw, C. Libby, A. Patankar, B. Bicer, *IEEE 46th Photovoltaic Specialists Conference (PVSC)* **2019**, 2475.
- [10] P. Sinha, V. L. Trumbull, S. W. Kaczmar, K. A. Johnson in *Energy science, engineering and technology* (Ed.: M. A. Gill), Nova Publishers, New York, **2014**, pp. 37–51.
- [11] G. TamizhMani, C. Libby, S. Shaw, R. Krishnamurthy, J. Leslie, R. Yadav, S. Tatapudi, B. Bicer in *2018 IEEE 7th World Conference on Photovoltaic Energy Conversion (WCPEC) (A Joint Conference of 45th IEEE PVSC, 28th PVSEC & 34th EU PVSEC)*, IEEE, **2018**.
- [12] Deponieverordnung, 27. April 2009 (BGBl. I S. 900), last change Artikel 3 der Verordnung vom 9. Juli 2021 (BGBl. I S. 2598).